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Book of Abstracts

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of various mass, charge states and energies will be presented. It will be discussed how the de-excitation is different in transmission experiments through 2D materials [4] and in grazing incidence scattering geometry from a surface [5]. In grazing incidence scattering it is possible to avoid surface-near processes such as the interatomic coulombic decay, which would otherwise lead to an ultra-fast (fs) de-excitation. We further present a comprehensive model calculation for highly excited HAs and their de-excitation cascade. Our code [5] takes radiative and non-radiative transition rates computed using the flexible atomic code (FAC) [6] as input and we account for screening and mirror charge effects. We find that for a free decay in vacuum the total lifetime of an HA is typically in the picosecond range. Additionally, we could show that under certain conditions, HAs can survive for up to 10 ps. This would make them in principle available for further studies and use in experiments.

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#C48: Collisions of electrons, atoms, and molecules, highly charged ions, astrophysical processes

Measuring ion-induced biomolecular fragmentation using a Velocity Map Imaging spectrometer

Antonin Bourgeteau; Alain Méry; Jimmy Rangama; Jean-Yves Chesnel; Violaine Vizcaino

CIMAP

The study of the interactions between ion beams and biomolecules such as nucleobases, nucleosides, amino acids or peptides is a relevant topic for hadrontherapy applications. After interaction with the energetic ions, the biomolecular target could be ionized and excited. Molecular fragmentation is one of the relaxation process for such ionized/excited states. To better quantify the fragmentation channels and the collision processes, it is interesting to measure the differential cross-sections of the created fragments in both kinetic energy (KE) and emission angle. The kinetic energy of the emitted fragment gives, indeed, information on the electronic state of the transient molecular ions prior dissociation. To do so, a Velocity Map Imaging (VMI) spectrometer initially designed to measure ion-induced electron emission from biologically relevant molecules [1] has been adapted to study fragmentation dynamics.

In the experimental set-up, the pulsed projectile ion beam crossed perpendicularly a continuous target beam produced from an effusive cell. The fragments formed in the interaction volume are velocity focused by a multi-electrode VMI spectrometer onto the 2D position sensitive detector (PSD) mounted after a flight tube. The time-of-flight (ToF) arrival signals are used to distinguish the fragments according to their m/q ratio with m and q , the mass and the charge state of fragment respectively. The detector is pulsed in order to image only a specific m/q specie determined by its ToF. An inverse Abel transform is then performed to the image to reconstruct the initial velocity vector and deduce both kinetic energy spectra and emission angle. The mass resolution of the spectrometer depends, in part, on the flight tube length. We have therefore designed a longer flight tube to improve the resolution, which allows us to access to both the kinetic energy and emission angle for many fragments of complex molecules that we could not separate before.

In this contribution, the new design of the VMI spectrometer will be presented. Moreover, the different fragmentation pathways of Uracil and Adenine upon 120keV-Ar⁸⁺ collision will be discussed based on the KE spectra measured. The influence of the target beam initial velocity on the images of fragments that leave with a low kinetic energy

will also be discussed. Indeed, due to Maxwell-Boltzmann velocity distribution of the target beam, the images are shifted and distorted, presenting a more elliptical shape. A deconvolution method using a Wiener filter has been implemented on the experimental images to remove the influence of the target initial speed with rather satisfactory results.

- [1] Nicolas Sens, Michal Ryszka, Jean-Christophe Pouilly, Alain Méry, Jean-Yves Chesnel, and Violaine Vizcaino. A velocity map imaging spectrometer for measuring absolute differential cross sections for ion-induced electron emission from molecules. Rev. Sci. Instrum. 93, 085103 (2022)5

#C49: Collisions of electrons, atoms, and molecules, highly charged ions, astrophysical processes

Electron-Induced Fluorescence of Carbon Monoxide

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The electron-induced fluorescence of carbon monoxide (CO) was studied in a crossed electron and molecule beam experiment using optical emission spectroscopy. CO is one of the dominant carbon bearing molecules in the Universe, especially on extra-terrestrial bodies such as comets or centaurs. Many of the previous publications are focused solely on the Comet Tail system of CO⁺ [1], because of its dominance in higher energy spectra, and the diagnostic of these cometary volatiles is a necessity for solar system formation models [2].

The emission spectrum following electron impact on CO was measured at 5-100 eV within the wavelengths range of 300-1000 nm. The emission bands of CO dominate this spectral region at energies below 20 eV, while the signal from CO⁺ becomes dominant above this energy. The 50 eV spectrum shows a prominent emission of the Comet Tail system of CO⁺ (A²Π - X²Σ⁺), along with a few emission bands of the Baldet-Johnson system of CO⁺ (B²Σ - A²Π⁺) and the emission lines of C I and O I. Excitation-emission functions of several emission bands were measured as well, and their threshold energies were estimated. Additionally, a 3D spectral electron energy map was created, consisting of emission spectra measured at energies ranging from 5 to 100 eV with small energy steps. These data provide detailed information about the excitation-emission functions of all individual transitions in the spectra and their threshold energies. The data is suitable as reference data not only for astrophysical research but for any field utilizing emission spectroscopy.

Fig.: The emission spectrum of CO measured by CCD camera at 50 eV (a) within 300-660 nm and (b) within 660-1000 nm. Excitation-emission functions: c) CO⁺ (B²Σ - X²Σ) at 230.3 nm, d) CO (b³Σ⁺ -

$a^3\Pi$) at 297.2 nm, e) CO ($a^3\Sigma^+ - a^3\Pi$) combined with CO^+ ($A^2\Pi - X^2\Sigma^+$) at 402.2 nm, f) CO ($B^1\Sigma^+ - A^1\Pi$) at 451.1 nm.

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#C50: Collisions of electrons, atoms, and molecules, highly charged ions, astrophysical processes

Transfer ionization dynamics in collisions involving light ions and helium atoms

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Transfer ionization (TI) is one of the processes that in the past 20 years allowed elucidating the role of target electron correlation in ion-atom collisions. A decade ago, fully differential cross sections which depend on the emitted electron momentum distribution were measured for $H^+ + He$ collisions at impact energies of 300 and 630 keV. This study allowed determining the dominant role of the initial state correlation over the dynamical correlation experienced by the electron in the reaction region or in the final state [1].

In this work, we explore the dynamics of TI in collisions of H^+ , He^{2+} and Li^{3+} ions with He atoms in the ground state. The impact energy range considered is 10 keV/u–1 MeV/u. Three different variants of the 4-body classical trajectory Monte Carlo (CTMC) method are employed: i) the nCTMC, in which the electrons are considered as independent particles initialized with sequential binding energies of 0.903 a.u. and 2.0 a.u. [2], ii) the Heisenberg core (HC-CTMC), which includes the e-e correlation via the introduction of momentum-dependent stabilizing potentials [3] and iii) the energy-bounded (EB-CTMC) [4], which also includes the full e-e correlation.

We found that according to our correlated model, TI events take mainly place while the projectile is still approaching the target. Moreover, electron capture seems to proceed first with a time difference between peak positions of about 0.5 a.u. of time. Results obtained with the three classical models are analyzed as a function of the impact energy.

The work was supported by the Bilateral relationships between Argentina and Hungary in science and technology (S&T) under project number 2019-2.1.11-TÉT-2020-00202. Work at IFISUR was supported by Grant No. PGI 24/F084, Secretaría General de Ciencia y Tecnología, Universidad Nacional del Sur.

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#C51: Collisions of electrons, atoms, and molecules, highly charged ions, astrophysical processes

Mutual neutralization reactions in collisions between pyrimidine cations and oxygen and chlorine atomic anions

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The formation and breakage of molecular bonds is at the core of understanding and controlling chemical reactions that determine our life, quality of terrestrial environment as well as evolution of the universe. Depending on the nature of the colliding species different chemical reactions can occur.

In particular, when two molecular ions interact, this can lead to the charge transfer from an anion to a cation, resulting in their mutual neutralisation (MN). Depending on the collision energy this process may lead to the formation of molecular bonds and new species, or to the separation of the two neutral species that are electronically excited. When one of the species is a polyatomic molecule, it can also be ro-vibrationally excited and undergo molecular dissociation as result of internal conversion from an electronic excited state or from head-on collisions (nuclear stopping).

In this work we took advantage of the unique opportunity offered by the cryogenic double electrostatic ion beam storage ring facility DE-SIREE [1-6] to study mutual neutralization reactions in ~100 meV collisions between pyrimidine cations and atomic anions. In these experiments we performed both two- and three-particle coincidence measurements to explore the charge transfer process at relatively large (oxygen anion) and short (chlorine anion) distances, as well as the following pyrimidine molecule fragmentation. These experiments, supported by Landau-Zener model calculations as well as molecular dynamics simulation, will provide fundamental understanding of biomolecular interactions in relatively complex systems.

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SAPP XXV

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ELECTRON INDUCED DISSOCIATIVE EXCITATION OF FORMAMIDE

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Formamide, the simplest amide, is an interesting system to study due to its C=O double bond and C-N peptide bond. Its diverse chemistry includes functional groups and chemical bonds found in key biomolecules, making it a candidate as a potential precursor to life, many biochemical studies propose it likely played a crucial role in the context of the origin of life on our planet. The emission spectrum following electron impact on formamide is studied in a crossed-beam experiment. The spectra were measured at three slit widths of 100 and 300 μm , all at 50 eV, within a wavelengths range of 280 to 1000 nm, to achieve optimal ratio of signal intensity and resolution. In the emission spectra, several lines and bands could be successfully identified, where the most prominent excited species that found were the hydrogen Balmer series, the nitrogen triplet system NH, the excited CH radical in the A and B electronic states, and atomic oxygen.

1. Introduction

Electron-induced fluorescence (EIF) is a technique enabling studying the electronic, vibrational, and rotational states of molecules through the principle of optical emission spectroscopy due to the emission of products from electron-molecule collisions; significantly important in several fields, such as interstellar chemistry (nebulae, stars, comets) [1].

Emission spectroscopy is an analytical method allowing the study of electron-molecule collisions producing excited species, which is especially important for astrophysics, particularly in space exploration, as it enables remote analysis of planetary atmospheres, cometary comas, and nebulae irradiated mainly by nearby stars [2]. The secondary electrons generated in photoionization reactions further interact with gas molecules and emission generated through these reactions provide insights into the molecular composition and processes active in these interstellar bodies.

In recent years, it has become evident that the chemistry of interstellar bodies is not confined to the gas phase. A significant portion of their mass resides in condensed matter, primarily in refractory dust grains or dust coated with volatile molecular ice mantles. Alternatively, ice-coated dust can accumulate on larger objects, growing in size up to that of comets. This process is of great interest to astrobiology, as comets are believed to play a role in delivering water and essential organic compounds to planetary surfaces. Such deliveries, including those to early Earth, could have occurred at a critical time, potentially contributing to prebiotic processes that led to the emergence of life [3].

Formamide (NH_2CHO) has been identified as a potential precursor to a wide variety of organic compounds essential for life, and many biochemical studies propose that it likely played a crucial role in the origin of life on Earth. First, it has an amide functional group ($-\text{N}-\text{C}(=\text{O})-$), which is necessary to form chains of aminoacids and build up proteins; and second, it has been identified as a key precursor of a large variety of prebiotic molecules. Its first detection in space was reported in 1971 in the Sagittarius B2 region (Sgr B2), the most massive star-forming region in our galaxy. Additionally, its detection in comets, that retained their chemical composition from the birth of the Solar System, raises the question of whether a significant amount of formamide may have been exogenously delivered to the young Earth around four billion years ago [4-5].

The data from previous research on electron-induced fluorescence of formamide are insufficient or practically non-existent for studying extraterrestrial bodies. This study aims to expand the database of

absolute emission cross sections and provide detailed information on the processes occurring during the experiments.

2. Experimental Apparatus

The experimental apparatus used in this work is based on a crossed electron and molecular beams method and is further described in a previous publication [6]. Trochoidal electron monochromator located in a vacuum chamber generates a monochromatic electron beam. The electron beam interacts with a perpendicular molecular beam formed by an effusive capillary. The background pressure of the vacuum chamber is $\sim 10^{-8}$ mbar and the pressure of the molecular beam is set to sustain binary interactions – one electron with one molecule. One of the products of electron-molecule interactions are excited species. These are unstable and emit radiation as they de-excite. The emitted radiation is collected by a UV fused silica lens and guided out of the vacuum chamber to a parabolic mirror, which focuses this radiation to the entrance slit of a Czerny-Turner optical monochromator. To maximise the detected signal, a spherical mirror is placed opposite to the collecting lens with its focus at the centre of collision. To acquire signal from the emitted radiation, an Andor iDUS 420 CCD camera is used. The CCD camera is sensitive to 300 – 1100 nm wavelength range and can obtain signal from an approximately 85 nm interval of wavelengths.

3. Experimental results and discussion

In a first step of this experiment, the emission spectrum of formamide was measured using different slit widths (100 μm and 300 μm which correspond to spectral resolution 0.4 nm and 1 nm), at 50eV electron energy. Comparing the experimental results allows us to determine the optimal measurement parameters for analyzing formamide, aiming the best resolution to identify the peaks and bands corresponding to the emission excitation of all possible fragmentations of the compound. The first emission spectrum, obtained with a slit width of 100 μm , was measured in the wavelengths within 300 – 950 nm. Meanwhile, the emission spectra with slit width of 300 μm was measured over a shorter wavelength range within 300 – 500 nm.

Comparing the emission spectra obtained, several emission lines were identified. In the spectrum 100 μm slit width, it is possible to observe the emission line corresponding to H_α as well as the oxygen emission line in the IR wavelength region, $\text{O I } (3p^3P-3s^3S^0)$, as shown in figure 1. In both spectra, the most prominent emission line corresponds to the nitrogen triplet system $\text{NH } (A^3\Pi-X^3\Sigma)$, and the rest of the hydrogen's Balmer series from H_β to H_n , were also identified along with the $\text{CH } (B^2\Sigma-X^2\Sigma)$, $\text{CH } (A^2\Delta-X^2\Pi)$ and $\text{CN } (B^2\Sigma-X^2\Sigma)$ bands, as shown in figure 2 [7 – 8].

Formamide is a liquid under typical temperature and pressure conditions at the Earth's surface. It is volatile and has a relatively low boiling point. However, conducting measurements of this compound proved to be more challenging than anticipated, as it condenses easily, leading to blockages in the system. Therefore, it is crucial to properly regulate the temperature of each individual component of the system to prevent condensation and subsequent blockages. At the same time, it is necessary to identify the ideal conditions to maintain a sufficiently high pressure that ensures a reasonable signal intensity.

The results presented are preliminary and help to clarify the most suitable parameters for working with this type of sample, allowing us to achieve clear, well-defined, stable, and reproducible results. We will continue working by repeating the measurements until the optimal working conditions are determined. Subsequently, a more comprehensive study of this molecule will be conducted, obtaining the emission spectrum after electron beam collisions at different electron energies ranging from 5 to 100 eV, covering the wavelength range from 280 to 1000 nm.

Fig. 1. The emission spectrum of Formamide measured by CCD camera at 50 eV electron energy with slit width of 100 μm , from 500 to 950 nm.

Fig. 2. The emission spectrum of Formamide measured by CCD camera at 50 eV electron energy with slit widths of 100 μm and 300 μm , from 300 to 500 nm.

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SAPP XXV

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and

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LOW ENERGY ELECTRONS INTERACTION WITH ACETONE (CH₃)₂CO IN THE UV-VIS SPECTRAL REGION

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Various studies have explored different aspects of electron-molecule interactions, which are fundamental processes in plasma chemistry, atmospheric reactions, astrophysics, and cometary science. Acetone occurs naturally in the human body, plants, and the atmosphere, and is also synthesized as a manufactured chemical used in cleaning products, paints, coatings, pharmaceuticals, and more [1]. Acetone is also an organic compound detected in extraterrestrial environments, including interstellar space, protoplanetary disks, and the surfaces of comets. For example, Douglas N. Friedel et al. (2005) reported the detection of interstellar acetone in the Orion-KL hot core, a high-mass star-forming region [2]. In 2017, a study on the evolution of cometary nuclei surfaces confirmed the presence of acetone and methanol through the sublimation of ice in the presence of organic volatiles [3]. The detection of significant abundances of acetone in various extra-terrestrial environments, such as comets, interstellar space, and planetary atmospheres, has significant implications for chemical processes, prebiotic chemistry, and astrobiology. Therefore, understanding the elementary processes and kinetics of electron-impact reactions on acetone is essential. In astronomy, the accurate description of emission spectra is particularly important, as most astronomical objects are primarily studied using emission spectroscopy.

Several studies have examined the fluorescence of acetone induced by various sources. The shape of the emission spectrum can reveal whether the emission is induced by electrons, photons, or other sources and provides insights into the excitation reaction energy. For example, Damon and Daniels [4] were the first to report fluorescence in acetone vapor when exposed to ultraviolet light from a mercury arc. T. Tran et al. investigated the fluorescence of acetone induced by a laser at pressures ranging from 1 to 15 atm [5]. However, only a few studies have explored the electron-impact spectrum of acetone. Our study focuses on the interaction of acetone molecules with low-energy electrons (10–100 eV) using emission spectroscopy in the UV-Vis spectral region. Electron-induced fluorescence (EIF) is a phenomenon that occurs during inelastic collisions of low-energy electrons with molecules based on a crossed electron and molecular beams method. At the Laboratory of Electron-Induced Fluorescence (LEIF) at Comenius University in Bratislava, optical emission spectra of acetone species under electron impact are currently being reported. The most prominent spectral features in the emission spectrum of acetone ((CH₃)₂CO) were measured in the wavelength range of 280 – 950 nm at 50 eV electron energy, including the hydrogen Balmer series lines H α at 656.3 nm and H β at 486 nm, the Swan system of C₂ (d³ Π g–a³ Π u) within 460–472 nm, and the CH (A² Δ –X² Π) emission band observed in the range of 415–445 nm as shown in Fig. 1. These processes involve photon emission following electron-impact excitation and the subsequent de-excitation of excited particles. The emphasis is on spectral analysis and the determination of emission cross-sections. The primary objective of this work is to obtain data on the electron-induced fluorescence of acetone molecules in a crossed-beam experiment, which are key components in many extraterrestrial environments and may play a crucial role in astrophysics.

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WATER EMISSION INDUCED BY LOW-ENERGY ELECTRON IMPACT

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Electron induced excitation reactions of water were studied by means of optical emission spectroscopy in the spectral range between 200 nm and 800 nm in crossed beams experiment. Excited water cation H_2O^+ , fragments OH, OH^+ and H and O were identified in the spectrum. For most intensive transition the cross sections and threshold energies were determined.

1. Introduction

Electron induced processes are abundant in various environments from space, planetary atmospheres through industry to laboratory. In astrophysics using the optical emission spectroscopic methods they can act as remote probe of physical properties of environments since every molecule or atom has a unique spectrum.

Analysis of the data from the Rosetta mission to comet 67P/Churyumov-Gerasimenko shown that the emission from the comet coma is induced mostly by electron impact outside the 2 AU pre-perihelion [1]. The emission fades if the comet is within 2 AU of the Sun. The effect can be caused by increased concentration of water in the coma leading to different energy distribution of electrons [2]. To assess such effect, it is necessary to thoroughly study the electron impact fluorescence of water including the cross sections in laboratory conditions as current data are incomplete or insufficient.

2. Experiment

Fig. 1. Experimental apparatus

The apparatus used for the experiment was described in detail in previous publication [3] and is schematically depicted in figure 1. It utilized crossed beams configuration. The sources of electron (trochoidal electron monochromator) and molecular beams (effusive capillary) are in a vacuum

chamber with background pressure of $\sim 10^{-8}$ mbar. The experiments were carried out at $\sim 1.5 \times 10^{-4}$ mbar. We have checked the linearity of the spectral line intensities on the pressure so that the single collision conditions were maintained [4]. The fluorescence radiation was collected by an optical system located perpendicularly to the crossing beams which focused the fluorescence signal onto the entrance slit of the Oriel Cornerstone 260 Czerny-Turner $\frac{1}{4}$ m optical monochromator. After passing through the optical monochromator, the signal was detected by a low-noise, Peltier-cooled photomultiplier working in the photon counting regime. The measurement was done in two modes: spectral measurement at constant electron energy or cross section measurement at specific wavelength corresponding to one deexcitation. The energy of the electron beam was absolutely calibrated by introducing a mixture of N_2 and H_2O into the apparatus and by measuring the intensity profile of the N_2 ($C^3\Pi_u-B^3\Pi_g$)(0-0) band at 337 nm which exhibits relatively sharp maximum at 14.1 eV [5] and intensity profile of H_β line. Subsequently the profile of H_β line was aligned with the same measurement in pure water vapours to calibrate the electron energy.

3. Results and discussion

The spectral region between 200 nm and 900 nm has been studied. The spectrum shown in the figure 2 is corrected for the spectral sensitivity of the experimental device. In the spectrum measured at electron energy 50eV the emission corresponding to deexcitation of atomic hydrogen (Balmer series), OH ($A^2\Sigma^+-X^2\Pi$), OH^+ ($A^3\Pi-X^3\Sigma^+$) and H_2O^+ ($\tilde{A}^2A_1-X^2B_1$) have been detected. The spectral bands corresponding to OH, OH^+ and H_2O^+ were identified according to the [6] and [7].

Fig. 2. Emission spectrum of water induced by 50 eV electrons impact.

In the spectral region above 800 nm no line nor band has been identified. One of the reasons can also be relatively low detector sensitivity. The O I ($3s^5S^0 - 3p^5P$) at 777 nm line is very faint, almost hidden within the detector noise. The detail of the OH (A-X) transition is shown in the figure 3 including the region below 300 nm. All the detected water cation band correspond to the various vibrational transitions of H_2O^+ (A-X) and are present between 450 nm and 750 nm.

Fig. 3. Emission spectrum showing the detail of OH (A-X) transition measured at 50 eV electrons impact.

Apart from the spectral measurement the cross sections for the most intensive transitions were determined as well. The curves for Balmer's series were measured for transition H (3-2) to H (7-2). For each cross section the threshold energy was determined by simple fitting procedure. These values were compared to theoretical thresholds based on enthalpy of formation. The cross section curve for H (4-2) transition is shown in the figure 4.

Fig. 4. Cross section curves of OH (A-X), OH+ (A-X), H₂O+ (A-X) and H (4-2) transitions.

From the curve shape it is evident that there are three distinct thresholds. These correspond to different generation channels of excited hydrogen atoms in the electron-molecule reaction. Similar shape can be seen in case of other Balmer's series lines as well.

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ELECTRON INDUCED DISSOCIATIVE EXCITATION OF FORMAMIDE

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Introduction

Formamide [NH₂CHO], the simplest amide, is an interesting system to study due to its functional groups and chemical bonds, making it a candidate as a potential precursor to life. Its first detection in space was reported in 1971 in the Sagittarius B2 region (Sgr B2). Additionally, its detection in comets, that retained their chemical composition from the birth of the Solar System, raises the question of whether a significant amount of formamide may have been exogenously delivered to the young Earth around four billion years ago [1-2].

Fig.1: Chemical structure formula and three-dimensional structure of Formamide.

Fig.2: Scheme of electron induced fluorescence apparatus.

Experimental setup

The experimental setup is located at Comenius University in Bratislava, Slovakia; is further described in a previous publication [3]. In summary, a trochoidal electron monochromator (TEM) is placed inside a vacuum chamber to generate a monochromatic electron beam, thermally emitted from a tungsten filament (Agar Scientific A054), which collide perpendicularly with a molecular beam produced by an effusive capillary. The electron induced emission spectra are measured using a Czerny–Turner optical monochromator, which provides a spectral resolution from 0.3 nm to 1 nm FWHM and is equipped with a Andor iDUS 420 CCD camera sensitive to wavelengths between 300 to 1100 nm and a Hamamatsu photomultiplier tube (PMT) operating in the photon counting mode, operating in the 185-700nm wavelength range.

Fig. 3: The emission spectrum of Formamide measured by CCD camera at 50 eV electron energy with slit width of 100 μm and 300 μm, from 300 to 500 nm.

Experimental results

The nitrogen triplet system NH (A³Π-X³Σ), and the hydrogen's Balmer series from H_β to H_η, were identified along with the CH (B²Σ-X²Σ), CH (A²Δ-X²Π) and CN (B²Σ-X²Σ) bands, as shown in figure 3. In the spectrum 100 μm slit width, it is possible to observe the emission line corresponding to H_α as well as the oxygen emission line in the IR wavelength region, OI (3p³P-s³S⁰), as shown in figure 4.

The excitation emission functions at a fixed wavelength was measured as well. These correspond to specific transitions, as shown in figure 5a and 5b. The curves give the information about the probability of the given process occurrence and the threshold energy of the process.

Fig. 5: excitation emission function of a) NH (A-X) and b) CH(B-X) + CN(B-X).

Fig. 4: The emission spectrum of Formamide measured by CCD camera at 50 eV electron energy with slit widths of 100 μm from 500 to 950 nm.

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Electron Induced Dissociative Excitation of Formamide

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Electron-induced fluorescence (EIF) is a technique that enables the study of excited species of molecules after collision with an electron, based on the principle of optical emission spectroscopy, which is particularly important in astrophysics, especially in space exploration, as it allows for the remote analysis of interstellar bodies irradiated by nearby stars [1].

Formamide (NH_2CHO) has been identified as a potential precursor to a wide variety of organic compounds essential for life, and many biochemical studies propose that it likely played a crucial role in the origin of life on Earth. It contains an amide functional group ($-\text{N}-\text{C}(=\text{O})-$), which is necessary to form chains of aminoacids and build up proteins; and it has been identified as a key precursor of numerous prebiotic molecules [2]. Its first detection in space was reported in 1971 in the Sagittarius B2 region (Sgr B2). Additionally, its detection in comets, that retained their chemical composition from the birth of the Solar System, raises the question of whether a significant amount of formamide may have been exogenously delivered to early Earth [2].

The previously published data on the electron-induced fluorescence of formamide are insufficient for studying extraterrestrial bodies. Since the emission spectroscopy is one of the main analytical methods in astronomy, it is necessary to have reliable reference data produced at stable repeatable conditions in laboratory. Many astronomical spectra are very complex as the photon signal is produced by various processes at once. In these cases, modelling can provide more insight but for models to be reliable the input data quality is crucial. The reactions cross sections are often used as input for models but the lack of reliable published data leads to lower quality models. This study aims to expand the database of absolute emission cross sections and provide detailed information on the process kinetics occurring during the experiments.

The emission spectrum following electron impact on formamide is studied in a crossed-beam experiment. The spectra were measured at slit widths of 100 and 300 μm , at 50 eV, within a wavelengths range of 280 to 1000 nm, to achieve optimal ratio of signal intensity and resolution. In the emission spectra, several lines and bands could be successfully

identified, as the Hydrogen Balmer series, the nitrogen triplet system NH ($A^3\Pi-X^3\Sigma$), the excited CH ($B^2\Sigma-X^2\Sigma$), CH ($A^2\Delta-X^2\Pi$) and CN ($B^2\Sigma-X^2\Sigma$) bands, and the atomic oxygen emission line in the IR wavelength region, OI ($3p^3P-s^3S^0$), as is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. The emission spectrum of Formamide measured by CCD camera at 50 eV electron energy with slit widths of 100 μm and 300 μm , from 300 to 500 nm.

The results presented are preliminary and help to clarify the most suitable parameters for working with this type of sample, allowing us to achieve clear, well-defined, stable, and reproducible results. Subsequently, a more comprehensive study of this molecule will be conducted, obtaining the emission spectrum after electron beam collisions at different electron energies ranging from 5 to 100 eV, covering the wavelength range from 280 to 1000 nm.

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Low energy electrons interaction with acetone $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CO}$ in the UV-Vis spectral region

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This study investigates the interaction of acetone molecules with low-energy electrons (10–100 eV) using emission spectroscopy in the UV-Vis spectral region, with a focus on spectral analysis and the determination of emission cross-sections. The primary objective is to obtain data on the electron-induced fluorescence of $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CO}$ molecules, which are significant components of many extraterrestrial objects and hold substantial potential in astrophysical research. The processes of electron impact fluorescence methods enable the study of the electronic, vibrational, and rotational state of molecules, as well as the exploration of dissociation excitation, ionization, and photon emission processes.

Electron collisions with molecules are fundamental processes in plasma chemistry, atmospheric reactions, astrophysics, and comets. The detection of significant amounts of acetone in various extraterrestrial environments, such as comets, interstellar space, and planetary atmospheres, has significant implications for chemical processes, prebiotic chemistry, and astrobiology. At the Laboratory of Electron-Induced Fluorescence (LEIF) at Comenius University in Bratislava, optical emission spectra of acetone species under electron impact are currently being reported as shown in Fig. 1. The most prominent spectral features (hydrogen Balmer series, Swan system, and the CH $(\text{A}^2\Delta\text{-X}^2\Pi)$ emission band) in the emission spectrum of CH_3COCH_3 were measured in the wavelength range of 280 – 950 nm at 50 eV electron energy [1].

Reference

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Figure 1: The emission spectrum of $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CO}$ was measured by a CCD camera at 50 eV electron energy. The excitation emission functions of H_β , H_γ , and Q_1 branch of CH $(\text{A}^2\Delta\text{-X}^2\Pi)$ were measured in the electron energy range within 10–100 eV using the photomultiplier as a detector, as shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Excitation emission functions of a) H_β at 486 nm, b) H_γ combined with CH $(\text{A}^2\Delta\text{-X}^2\Pi)$ at 433.9 nm, c) Q_1 branch of CH $(\text{A}^2\Delta\text{-X}^2\Pi)$ at 430.8 nm, and d) H_γ with subtracted signal from CH $(\text{A}^2\Delta\text{-X}^2\Pi)$ at 433.9 nm.

Electron Induced Dissociative Excitation of Formamide

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Abstract. Formamide is an interesting molecule. It is the simplest amide, with a C=O double bond and a C-N peptide bond that contributes to a diverse chemical composition, including functional groups and chemical bonds present in key biomolecules, making it a candidate precursor to life. Numerous biochemical studies suggest that it likely played a crucial role in the origin of life on our planet. The emission spectrum following electron impact on formamide was studied in a crossed-beam experiment. The spectra were measured at two slit widths of 100 and 300 μm , with electron energy set at 50 eV, within a wavelength range of 280 to 1000 nm, to achieve an optimal ratio of signal intensity and resolution. In the emission spectra, several lines and bands could be successfully identified. The most prominent excited species that were found were the hydrogen Balmer series, the nitrogen triplet system NH, the excited CH radical in the A and B electronic states, and atomic oxygen.

Introduction

Electron-induced fluorescence (EIF) is a technique that allows the study of the electronic, vibrational and rotational states of molecules through the principle of optical emission spectroscopy, an analytical method based on the study of the emission of excited species resulting from electron-molecule collisions. It is important in various fields, such as interstellar chemistry [Blasko *et al.*, 2023], since it allows the remote analysis of planetary atmospheres, cometary comas and nebulae irradiated mainly by nearby stars [Bodewits *et al.*, 2019]. Secondary electrons generated in photoionization reactions also interact with gas molecules and the emission generated through these reactions provides information about the molecular composition and active processes in these interstellar bodies.

In recent years, it has become evident that the chemistry of interstellar bodies is not confined to the gas phase. A significant portion of their mass resides in condensed matter, primarily in refractory dust grains or dust coated with volatile molecular ice mantles. Alternatively, ice-coated dust can accumulate on larger objects, growing in size up to that of comets. This process is of great interest to astrobiology, as comets are believed to play a role in delivering water and essential organic compounds to planetary surfaces. Such deliveries, including those to early Earth, could have occurred at a critical time, potentially contributing to prebiotic processes that led to the emergence of life [Woond D., 2002].

Formamide (NH_2CHO) has been identified as a potential precursor to a wide variety of organic compounds essential for life, and many biochemical studies propose that it likely played a crucial role in the origin of life on Earth. First, it has an amide functional group ($-\text{N}-\text{C}(=\text{O})-$), which is necessary to form chains of amino acids and build up proteins, and second, it has been identified as a key precursor of a large variety of prebiotic molecules. Its first detection in space was reported in 1971 in the Sagittarius B2 region (Sgr B2), the most massive star-forming region in our galaxy. Additionally, its detection in comets that retained their chemical composition from the birth of the Solar System, raises the question of whether a significant amount of formamide may have been exogenously delivered to the young Earth around four billion years ago [López-Sepulcre *et al.*, 2019, Kahane *et al.*, 2013].

The data from previous research on electron-induced fluorescence of formamide are insufficient or practically non-existent for studying extraterrestrial bodies. This study aims to expand the database of absolute emission cross sections and provide detailed information on the processes occurring during the experiments.

Experimental Apparatus

The experimental apparatus used in this work is based on the crossed-beam method between electron and molecular beams and is further described in a previous publication [Országh *et al.*, 2017]. A trochoidal electron monochromator located in a vacuum chamber generates a monochromatic electron beam. The electron beam interacts with a perpendicular molecular beam formed by an effusive capillary. The background pressure of the vacuum chamber is $\sim 10^{-8}$ mbar, and the pressure of the molecular beam is set to sustain binary interactions – one electron with one molecule. Among the products of electron-molecule interactions are excited species. These are unstable and emit radiation as they de-excite. The emitted radiation is collected by a UV fused silica lens and guided out of the vacuum chamber to a parabolic mirror, which focuses this radiation to the entrance slit of a Czerny-Turner optical monochromator. To maximize the detected signal, a spherical mirror is placed opposite to the collecting lens with its focus at the centre of collision. To acquire the emitted radiation, an Andor iDUS 420 CCD camera or a photomultiplier tube (PMT) is used. The CCD camera is sensitive to the 300 – 1100 nm wavelength range and can detect signals across an approximately 85 nm interval; meanwhile the PMT can operate in the region of 185 – 700 nm, collecting the signal from one small wavelength interval defined by optical resolution of the monochromator at a time.

The calibration of the measured data was done in several steps. First, the calibration of electron energy was performed by measuring the excitation-emission function of the vibrational transition (0,0) of the Second Positive system of N_2 at 337.1 nm. This transition has a well-defined maximum at 14.1 eV [Zubek *M.*, 1994]. Following the electron energy calibration, the recorded spectra were corrected for the spectral sensitivity of the experimental apparatus, in order to get correct relative values of intensity of the individual transitions. The apparatus sensitivity function for the PMT was determined in two steps. For wavelengths above 450 nm, the emission from a heated tungsten filament placed in the reaction chamber was measured and compared to the theoretical blackbody radiation described by Planck's law. The filament temperature was measured by a pyrometer. For the wavelength region below 450 nm, the sensitivity function is acquired by measuring the H_2 ($a^3\Sigma_g^+ - b^3\Sigma_u^+$) continuum at 14 eV and comparing it to the previously measured spectrum at the same energy by James *et al.* [James *et al.*, 1998]. The intensity scale of the spectra is relative. The apparatus sensitivity function for the CCD camera configuration was obtained by measuring the emission spectrum of N_2 at 25 eV energy. The spectrum was then compared to the already measured spectrum of N_2 at the same electron energy by [Magina *et al.*, 2011].

Experimental results and discussion

In a first step of this experiment, the emission spectrum of formamide was measured using different slit widths (100 μm and 300 μm which correspond to spectral resolution 0.4 nm and 1 nm), at 50 eV electron energy. Comparing the experimental results allows us to determine the optimal measurement parameters for analyzing formamide, aiming the best resolution to identify the peaks and bands corresponding to the emission excitation of all possible fragmentations of the compound.

Figure 1. The emission spectrum of Formamide measured by CCD camera at 50 eV electron energy with slit widths of 100 μm and 300 μm , from 300 to 500 nm.

The first emission spectrum, obtained with a slit width of 100 μm , was measured in the wavelengths within 300 – 950 nm. Meanwhile, the emission spectra with slit width of 300 μm was measured over a shorter wavelength range within 300 – 500 nm.

Comparing the emission spectra obtained, several emission lines were identified. In both spectra, the most prominent emission line corresponds to the nitrogen triplet system NH ($A^3\Pi-X^3\Sigma$), and the rest of the hydrogen's Balmer series from H_β to H_η , were also identified along with the CH ($B^2\Sigma-X^2\Sigma$), CH ($A^2\Delta-X^2\Pi$) and CN ($B^2\Sigma-X^2\Sigma$) bands, as shown in figure 1 [Luque *et al.*, 1999; Pearse *et al.*, 1976]. In the spectrum 100 μm slit width, from 500 nm to 950 nm it is possible to observe the emission line corresponding to H_α as well as the oxygen emission line in the IR wavelength region, O I ($3p^5P-3s^5S^0$), as shown in figure 2.

Figure 2. The emission spectrum of Formamide measured by CCD camera at 50eV electron energy with slit width of 100 μm , from 500 to 950nm.

Figure 3. Excitation-emission functions of the transitions: a) NH ($A^3\Pi-X^3\Sigma$) at 336.3 nm, b) CH ($B^2\Sigma-X^2\Sigma$) with CN ($B^2\Sigma-X^2\Pi$) at 386.0 nm and c) the overlapping of CH ($B^2\Sigma-X^2\Pi$), CN ($B^2\Sigma-X^2\Sigma$) and H_c at 388.8 nm.

Relative excitation-emission functions of the most prominent transitions were measured in the electron energy range within 10–100 eV using the PMT as detector. The functions are shown in figure 3. The excitation-emission function measured at 336.3nm (figure 3.a) contains the signal from NH ($A^3\Pi-X^3\Sigma$) emission band, meanwhile at 386.0 nm and at 388.8 nm were obtained the excitation emission function corresponding to CH ($B^2\Sigma-X^2\Sigma$) + CN ($B^2\Sigma-X^2\Pi$) (figure 3.b) and CH ($B^2\Sigma-X^2\Pi$) + CN ($B^2\Sigma-X^2\Sigma$) + H_ζ (figure 3.c). The aim of this results is to obtain information about the probability of the given proces occurrence, the individual threshold energy of the process and the dependency of the radiation intensity on the electron energy.

Conclusions

Formamide is a liquid under standard temperature and pressure conditions on Earth's surface. It is volatile and has a relatively low boiling point. However, conducting measurements with this compound proved more challenging than expected, as it tends to condense easily, leading to blockages in the system. Therefore, it is essential to carefully regulate the temperature of each individual component to prevent condensation and ensure uninterrupted flow. At the same time, it is necessary to identify the optimal conditions to maintain a sufficiently high pressure that guarantees reasonable signal intensity.

The results presented here are preliminary, but they help define the most suitable experimental parameters for working with this type of sample, allowing us to obtain clear, well-defined, stable, and reproducible data. Further work will involve repeating the measurements in order to carry out a more comprehensive study of this molecule, extracting the individual excitation-emission functions of selected transitions, comparing experimental and theoretical threshold energies, and acquiring a well-resolved spectrum in the 370–400 nm range. This will enable the clear identification of individual transitions corresponding to the CH ($B^2\Sigma-X^2\Pi$) and CN ($B^2\Sigma-X^2\Sigma$) band systems.

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Low-energy electrons interaction with acetone (CH₃)₂CO in the UV-Vis spectral region

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In this work, we present an experimental study focused on the low-energy electron impact excitation of acetone. Acetone was excited by quasi-monochromatic electrons generated by a trochoidal electron monochromator (TEM). In the emission spectrum, the most important excited species were found to be the hydrogen Balmer series, the excited CH radical in the A and B electronic states, and atomic carbon. The acetone emission spectrum was measured at several different reaction energies (10 -100 eV), forming a unique 3D spectral electron energy map. Excitation-emission functions were extracted for the selected most prominent products at fixed wavelengths, and their corresponding threshold energies were determined.

Introduction

This study investigates the interaction of acetone molecules with low-energy electrons (10–100 eV) using emission spectroscopy in the UV-Vis spectral region, focusing on spectral analysis and the determination of emission cross-sections. The primary objective is to obtain data on the electron-induced fluorescence of (CH₃)₂CO molecules, which are significant components of many extraterrestrial objects and hold substantial potential in astrophysical research. The electron impact fluorescence method enables the study of the electronic, vibrational, and rotational states of molecules, as well as the exploration of dissociation excitation, ionization if the photon emission is present.

Electron collisions with molecules are fundamental processes in plasma chemistry, atmospheric reactions, astrophysics, and comets. The detection of significant amounts of acetone in various extra-terrestrial environments, such as comets, interstellar space, and planetary atmospheres, has significant implications for chemical processes, prebiotic chemistry, and astrobiology. At the Laboratory of Electron-Induced Fluorescence (LEIF) at Comenius University in Bratislava, optical emission spectra of acetone under electron impact are reported as shown in Fig. 1. In our study, a crossed-beams apparatus was used to investigate electron impact fluorescence (EIF) [Danko et al. 2013]. The most prominent spectral features (hydrogen Balmer series, Swan system C²(d³Πg–a³Πu), and the CH (A²Δ–X²Π) emission band) in the emission spectrum of CH₃COCH₃ were measured in the wavelength range of 280 – 950 nm at 50 eV electron energy.

Figure 1. The emission spectrum of $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CO}$ was measured by a CCD camera at 50 eV electron energy.

The active region ranges between 380-445 nm of the emission spectra of our measurement in Fig. 1 was obtained with high resolution of up to 0.4 nm and corrected for the apparatus sensitivity as presented in Fig. 2. These enable us to identify individual rotational transitions from P, Q, R branches of CH fragments were identified according to Pearse [Pearse and Gaydon 1976] and LIFBASE 2.1.1 spectroscopy tool [Luque and Crosley 1999].

Figure 2. Higher resolution emission spectrum of $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CO}$ measured at 50 eV and calibrated for apparatus sensitivity. The rotational structures were identified.

The emission spectrum of acetone within the wavelength range of 380-450 nm was further recorded at several electron energies, ranging from 10 eV to 100 eV in 5 eV increments. These spectra form a 3D spectral electron energy map for transitions within the selected spectral range. The graph of the acetone spectra is presented in Fig. 3.

Figure 3. The 3D spectral electron energy map of acetone was measured at multiple electron energies ranging from 10 to 100 eV.

Figure 4. Excitation emission functions of a) H_{β} at 486 nm, b) H_{γ} combined with CH($A^2\Delta-X^2\Pi$) at 433.9 nm, c) Q_1 branch of CH ($A^2\Delta-X^2\Pi$) at 430.8 nm, and d) H_{γ} with subtracted signal from CH($A^2\Delta-X^2\Pi$) at 433.9 nm.

Discussion

The electron-induced emission spectrum of acetone at an incident electron energy of 50 eV was recorded over the wavelengths range of 280–950 nm, and the emission spectrum contained dissociated fragments of acetone as depicted in Fig. 1. The main prominent features of the spectrum are the CH(A²Δ–X²Π), CH(B²Σ[–]–X²Π), and the emission lines of hydrogen's Balmer series spanning from H_α to H_η. In addition to these dominant features, weaker signals attributed to other dissociation products were identified. Specifically, the Swan system C²(d³Πg–a³Πu) was identified along with the C₂(C¹Πg–A¹Πu) emission band that belongs to the Deslandres d'Azambuja system. A weak intensity CH(C²Σ⁺–X²Π) band was also recognized, in the part of the spectrum where the intensity is multiplied by 15x (blue line). Finally, atomic oxygen emissions were detected in the infrared region, corresponding to the transitions OI(3p⁵P–3s⁵S⁰) and OI(3p³P–3s³S⁰).

From the emission spectrum obtained in the wavelength range of 280–950 nm, the region between 380–445 nm is the most active part of the spectrum. Consequently, this active region was measured with higher spectral resolution, up to 0.4 nm, and the data were corrected for the apparatus sensitivity, as shown in Figure 2. Due to the increased resolution, some low-intensity features were lost; therefore, high-resolution measurements were limited to the region where the signal was still detectable. The CH(A²Δ–X²Π) emission band comprises (v,v) vibrational transitions, while the weaker CH(B²Σ[–]–X²Π) band consists solely of the (0,0) vibrational transition. Additionally, several emission lines from the Balmer series of atomic hydrogen, ranging from H_γ to H_η, were observed within this spectral range.

Relative excitation–emission functions of H_β, H_γ, and the CH(A²Δ–X²Π) Q₁ branch were measured from 10–100 eV, with thresholds at 22.2, 22.1, and 20.1 eV, respectively (Figure 4(a, c, d)) using the photomultiplier as detector. The H_γ signal at 433.9 nm (Figure 4(b)) overlaps with CH(A²Δ–X²Π) emission; thus, the CH(A²Δ–X²Π) contribution was subtracted using its profile at 430.8 nm (Figure 4(c)), scaled based on relative intensities at 50 eV. The corrected H_γ excitation–emission function is shown in Figure 4(d).

Electron–molecule collisions are of great interest in astrophysics, atmospheric science, planetary science, and laboratory plasma research. Understanding the fundamental reaction mechanisms involved in these collisions provides deeper insight into the chemical evolution of space and significantly contributes to the modeling and identification of species in astrophysical environments. In this study, the emission from acetone induced by low-energy electron impact has been analyzed. A 3D spectral electron energy map was constructed over the energy range of 10–100 eV. For the most prominent excited products, excitation–emission curves were also determined.

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Electron induced fluorescence of formamide

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Understanding the composition of extraterrestrial bodies provides valuable insights into the origins of life and opens exciting possibilities for the future, including the search for extraterrestrial life and the potential colonization of other planets. Emission spectroscopy is particularly valuable in space exploration, as it enables remote analysis of planetary atmospheres, cometary comas, and nebulas irradiated mainly by nearby stars. Formamide, the simplest amide, is an interesting system to study due to its C=O double bond and C-N peptide bond. Its diverse chemistry includes functional groups and chemical bonds found in key biomolecules, making it a candidate as a potential precursor to life, many biochemical studies propose it likely played a crucial role in the context of the origin of life on our planet. The emission spectrum following electron impact on formamide is studied in a crossed-beam experiment. The spectrum is measured at 50eV within the wavelengths of 280 - 1030 nm, and the width of the slits was set to 100, 200 and 300 μm to achieve optimal ratio of signal intensity and resolution.

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This work was supported by the Slovak Research and Development Agency under the Contracts no. SK-PL-23-0050, APVV-19-0386 and APVV-23-0522, Slovak grant agency VEGA under projects nr. 1/0489/21 and 1/0553/22. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 871149. Funded by the EU NextGenerationEU through the Recovery and Resilience Plan for Slovakia under the project No. 09I01-03-V04 00047.